

Foreword

LIBRARIES OF THE FUTURE

Emerging Trends

Editors

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ONTOLOGY EDITING TOOLS: A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON FLUENT EDITOR AND PROTÉGÉ

-Abhijith, B. and K. G. Sudhier

Introduction

The tremendous growth in the field of ICT and its overwhelming applications in day-to-day life is beyond one can imagine. With this pace, it is pretty challenging to predict the future. One thing is for sure; machines will be a part of our life (now also), and Artificial intelligence (AI) tries to create machines that can solve problems, later learn and understand from them for the future. AI, a highly interdisciplinary field, needs expertise from linguistics, philosophy, and many other disciplines apart from Computer Science (Grewal, 2014). Tech giants such as Amazon, Facebook, Google, etc., are creating and applying numerous different AI techniques (Weichbroth, 2019) in their organizations for giving better service for users. The concept of the Semantic Web (Berners-Lee et al., 2001) can only be achieved with such a development in all aspects.

Semantic web and ontology

The present-day web is designed in such a manner, that a human can only understand it. But lack of machine-readable knowledge structure hinders the program or software from fully comprehending the content, affecting the quality of information retrieved (Cardoso & Sheth, 2006). The solution for this problem is trivial, and it is to formulate a method for representing the knowledge that programs can understand.

The Semantic Web (Berners-Lee et al., 2001) has been proposed as a web expansion in which information is given a well-defined meaning to allow machines and people to collaborate. Ontology is a knowledge representation utilized on the Semantic Web (Sim & Wong, 2004). Ontology, in general, is the conversion of a domain into a machine-readable format that is understandable by humans also.

Web Services were created to make the knowledge represented by ontologies on the Semantic Web accessible across various applications (McIlraith, Son, & Zeng, 2001). Semantic Web Services describe Web Services as ontology, allowing other applications to access and comprehend them (Ankolekar et al., 2002). In recent years, research on the semantic web and services has received much attention, and the two should become more integrated in the future (Lastra, 2006).

Ontology: concept and definitions

Ontology has different aspects. In philosophy, Ontology is the branch that studies concepts such as existence, being, becoming, and reality. It includes how entities are grouped into basic categories on the most fundamental level (Lawson, 2012). In Library and Information Science or Computer Science, ontologies have been increasingly used since the early 90s, especially in complex domains such as Bio-medicine, where the multitude of concepts and the need to deal computationally with resources described by them. This made significant changes and has urged the adoption of standard vocabularies (Smith et al., 2003).

It is an explicit, formal description of a shared conceptualization (Gruber, 1993). The term “explicitly” here refers to the kind of concepts adopted, and the restrictions on their usage are explicitly described. Formal denotes the way that the ontology ought to be machine-readable. Conceptualization means the theoretical model of some wonder on the universe by recognizing the significant concepts of that wonder. Common replicates the idea that an ontology seizure consistent information (Corcho et al., 2007). Ontologies have been classified based on various factors, i.e., type of language used, the accountability of the conceptualization, and general requirements (Geertsm & McCarthy, 2002).

Ontology editing tools

If the existing vocabulary in a particular knowledge domain is not sufficient or not good enough, one can make their ontology. Also, existing ontologies can be manipulated. For these purposes, ontology editors can be helpful. Two ontology editing tools, Protégé (Open-Source software) and Fluent Editor (Freeware) are considered here for study. An introductory note on them is given below. Detailed analysis will be provided later.

Fluent editor

Fluent Editor, a product of Cognitum Software House, is an excellent tool for developing and editing complex and simple ontologies that employ Controlled Natural Language (Seganti, Kapłański, & Zarzycki, 2015). It tries to provide facilities that are suitable to human users than its competitors. Usage of Controlled English as a knowledge modeling language is an example of that. It also stops one from entering into grammatical or syntactical errors using predictive editors (Angelov, & Enache, 2010). The screenshot of the Website of the Fluent Editor is given below.

Figure 1: Screenshot of the Fluent Editor Website

Protégé

Protégé project was started by Stanford University in the 1980s and is well maintained and developed. It helps programmers build and modify ontologies and knowledge-based systems (Musen, 2015). It is free and open-source and is one of the most widely used tools for ontology creation and merging (Negi & Malik, 2018). The screenshot of the Protégé website is given below

Figure 2: Screenshot of the Protégé Website

Related studies

Wide varieties of ontology editors with unique features exist on the web, and because of this reason itself, many authors tried to compare their performance. Some exciting papers are discussed in this section.

Stojanovic and Motik (2002) analyzed essential qualities that Ontology editors should keep during the changes are mentioned. Changes in the user's requirements and exploring new knowledge will necessitate evolution in the ontology editors. García-Barriocanal, Sicilia and Sánchez-Alonso (2005) listed the usability evaluation of ontology editors. Evaluation is performed by selecting people with no specific ontology-creation skills. They were told to create simple ontologies without giving any room for improvement. The quality of ontologies thus formulated are evaluated and attained a view on the usability of different ontology editors. Experts in other sectors create ontologies for representing knowledge structure in their domain. Day-Richter et al. (2007) created OBO-Edit—an open-source, platform-independent ontology editor for biologists. They are developed and maintained by the Gene Ontology Consortium.

Alatrish (2012) compared the performance of different Ontology Editors based on criteria that he formulated. Here five Ontology editors were taken (Apollo, OntoStudio, Protégé, Swoop, and TopBraid), and it was clear after the comparison that users need to identify their needs. For different purposes, different tools can be used. Siricharoen (2018) described researchers' choice of editors and tools for Ontology building and their opinions about them. The recommendations were mainly from 31 computer Science experts. Also, a comparison between beginners' and experts' views on different ontology editors was included. Horridge et al. (2019) gave an in-depth analysis on Web Protégé. It is a cloud-based application promoting collaborative efforts in ontology building. Features and facilities included in the latest versions were also discussed.

Scope of the study

There are many ontology editors available for different purposes. Protégé is considered the most popular (Negi & Malik, 2018). Fluent Editor is also a popular choice, and because of this reason itself, this comparison is relevant. This comparison will be helpful for the developers in selecting the right ontology editors considering their needs.

Objectives

Objectives of the study are:

- To compare the basic details of Fluent Editor and Protégé.
- To compare the software architecture of both Fluent Editor and Protégé
- To compare the usability tools of Fluent Editor and Protégé
- To discuss the additional features of both Fluent editor and Protégé

Methodology

The present study employed a survey to identify possible competitors for Protégé software, and an analytical approach was used to create some criteria for comparing the performance of Fluent editor with that Protégé. Three measures were adopted from Alatrish (2012). They are listed below:

- **Basic Details:** This portion includes basic details about developers and availability
- **Software architecture:** This portion includes the software architecture details of the Ontology Editing tools (standalone or Web-Based) and extensibility and Ontology storage.
- **Usability:** This point shows the presence of graphical editors and visualization tools. It also checks whether it allows collaborative work.

Discussion

As mentioned in the methodology, the comparison is conducted in three sections: basic details, software architecture, and usability tools.

Basic details

In this part, basic details of the ontology editing tools are compared. Features taken here for consideration are the developers' name, licensing agreement, Compatibility with different operating systems. Table 1 contains the data, and those were taken from their website itself.

Table 1: Comparison of Basic Details of Fluent Editor and Protégé

Feature	Fluent Editor	Protégé
Developers	Cognitum Software House	Stanford Center for Biomedical Informatics Research at the Stanford University School of Medicine.

Access	Free for Individual Developers, Open source projects, Academic purposes	Free and Open Source
Compatibility with Different Operating Systems	Supports only Windows	Supports: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Windows • Mac OS • Linux • Also, include Platform Independent version.
Latest Version	Released on: January 15, 2015 Version: 3.6.10.28710	Released on: March 14, 2019 Version: 5.5.0

The Fluent Editor is developed and maintained by Cognitum Software House. It is free for individual developers, academic projects, research, and other developmental activities (It is a freeware). One can freely download and install for the purposes noted above. But the tool only supports Windows Operating System. The latest version is 3.6.10.2870, and it was released on January 15, 2015. When it comes to Protégé, is developed and maintained by the Stanford Center for Biomedical Informatics Research at the Stanford University School of Medicine. It is a free and open-source software, and it can run on all three Operating Systems; Windows, Mac OS, Linux. A platform-independent version is also available. The latest version V 5.5.0, was released on March 14, 2019.

Software architecture

After describing the essential feature, the software architecture is tabulated here. Points from the discussion taken here are Semantic-Web Architecture, Extensibility, Ontology Storage, Supporting Languages, and Compatibility with other ontology tools. Table 2 contain the data.

Table 2: Comparison of Software Architecture of Fluent Editor and Protégé

Feature	Fluent Editor	Protégé
Semantic web architecture	Standalone	Standalone And web Based (WebProtégé)
Extensibility	Plugins, Custom Grammars, R plugins	Plugins
Ontology storage	File and DBMS	File and DBMS
With other ontology tools	Protégé	PROMPT, OKBC, JESS, FaCT and Jena
Import/ Export from Languages	OWL 2, OWL-DL, OWL-RL, SWRL, SPARQL, RDF, OCNL, SKOS	XML(S), RDF, OWL 2, OWL-DL, Excel, BioPortal and Data Master Clips, SWRL-IQ, SWRL, SPARQL, RDF, OCNL

Fluent Editor is a standalone tool, and it supports two plug-ins: Protege interoperability plugin(This helps in exporting or importing data from Protégé) and R Plugins. R plugins utilize R Ontology packages for visualizing and listing the content of the ontology. For the case of Protégé, it has both stand-alone and Web-based format (WebProtégé). It also supports wide varieties of Plug-ins. Both tools store ontology as file and DBMS, and both are fully compatible with most of the Semantic Web W3C standards.

USABILITY OF TOOLS

Features of usability tools are compared here. Points taken for consideration were Graphical Taxonomy and Prunes, Option for Zooms and Collaborative Working, Presence of Reasoners. Table 3 lists the details.

Table 3: Comparison of Usability Tools of Fluent Editor and Protégé

Feature	Fluent Editor	Protégé
Graphical taxonomy	Yes	Yes
Graphical prunes (views)	Yes	Yes
Zooms	Yes	Yes
Collaborative working	Yes	Yes
Reasoners	Yes	Yes

From the table, it is clear that when it comes to Graphical Taxonomy or Prunes, Options for Zoom or Collaborative Work, Presence of Reasoner for checking the internal constancy, both Fluent Editor and Protégé perform well. Both support features listed in the table.

Additional features

Apart from tabular data, some additional features of both tools were observed and discussed here for further comparison.

Feature unique to fluent editor

Some other features of the Fluent editor on topic-wise will be discussed here. But the first thing to note here is the interface. It has an MS Office-like interface, which is quite familiar to the users. Figure 3 is a Screenshot of the interface. The upper ribbon contains modules such as File, Home, Reference, and Tools, similar to MS Office Word 2016. This is an advantage since familiarity in aesthetics makes people more comfortable.

Ontology diagrams

With one click (using selected materialization profile), users can visualize the created ontology and interact with it. Figure 3 includes the visualization of an ontology (Pen Ontology), a sample ontology created for this purpose. The interface also allows editing ontologies with Natural Language quickly.

The company has developed a feature called “Controlled English,” utilized in their editor, which is more human-understandable.

Figure 3: Screenshot of the Fluent Editor Tool Interface

SWRL debugger

Semantic Web Rule Language (SWRL) is the language of Semantic Web used to express rules and logic. It is an excellent tool for building actual ontologies and expressing complex relations. The fluent editor is embedded with an inbuilt SWRL Debugger. It can be used to check what are the rules executed during materialization.

Protégé interoperability

Protégé excels in giving deep insights into the structure of Ontology were as Fluent Editor gives the actual meaning of the ontology. In Fluent editor, there is an option for providing a synchronized view of both in one place by using proper plugins. This feature is unique for Fluent Editor and valuable too.

R language package

R language is an excellent tool for statistical analysis. The fluent editor allows combining both ontologies and statistics for better quantitative and qualitative research in one place using an R language package to access ontologies (rOntorion).

Features unique to protégé

Protégé was developed by the Stanford Center for Biomedical Informatics Research at the Stanford University School of Medicine. It is the most famous ontology editor tool at present. Unlike Fluent Editor, Protégé’s interface is a new, unfamiliar, but at the same time simple one. Figure 4 is the screenshot of the Protégé interface.

Figure 4: Screenshot of the Protégé Interface

Ontology plugins

Protégé uses many plugins such as Jambalaya, OntoGraf, GraphViz, GROW, OntoSphere, etc. (Bosca, Bonino, & Pellegrino, 2005) for ontology visualization. Figure 4 is a visualization of sample Pen Ontology using the OntoGraf plugin. Like this, Plugin availability for various purposes is fascinating in the case of Protégé. It has a highly pluggable architecture.

Protégé community

Unlike Fluent Editor, Protégé has excellent community support. The protégé team also helps users through the interactive mailing list. At present, there are 36,6084 registered users for Protégé (Protégé Community, Accessed on 08, December 2021).

Conclusion

A comparison of Fluent Editor with Protégé brings on some interesting conclusions. Essential details as described in Table 1 show that even though both can be freely downloaded from the web, Fluent Editor is freeware and Protégé is open-source software. Both are free for individual and academic projects. One of the main drawbacks of Fluent Editor is that it can only be run on Windows. But Protégé is compatible with Windows, Mac, Linux, and a platform-independent format. Strong community support and availability of updates make Protégé the primary choice for developers. When usability tools were compared, both were performing well. Both support collaborative work, graphical taxonomy, reasoners, etc. For the case of software architecture, only Protégé has both standalone and web-based format (WebProtégé). The last update for Fluent editor came on January 15, 2015 (Version: 3.6.10.28710). Same time Protégé gives updates regularly. The Plugin compatibility and availability of ontology visualizing tools, supporting varieties of W3C standards are common to both tools. When it comes to interface, Fluent Editor manages to top because it resembles MS office Word. The Fluent Editor also provides a synchronized view of features offered by Protégé and Fluent editors. Considering all these comparisons, it can be concluded that both editors have their unique features. But regular updates and compatibility with different OS and

platforms, strong community supports, open-source features make Protégé the first choice when it comes to Ontology editing tools.

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